

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B108
Date: 05 Jul 2005
Take Off: 10:48:21Z
Landing: 15:40:48Z
Flight Time: 4h52m27s

Campaign: CWVS
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jonathan Smith	Leeds University
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	CVI / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	CCN / AMS	Jonny Crozier	Manchester University
9	ADA/CPI	Paul Connolly	Manchester University
10	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office
11			
12			
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14			
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17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B108 Track 05-JUL-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b108
 Date: 5 July 2005
 Project: CWVS
 Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
103301		INU to nav	0.42 kft	128	Cranfield 52'04.36N 00'37.48W
103553		engine start	0.42 kft	128	
103735		power change over	0.42 kft	128	
104821		T/O	4.4 kft	299	Cranfield 10:48:21
105202		ASPs	5.0 kft	279	ASPs open
105322		videos recording	5.0 kft	258	FFC (left) & DFC(right)
110541		HORACE/DRS/DLU	5.0 kft	180	check satis
111507	111510	Profile 1	5.0 kft	248	from 5000'
112909		interrupt profile 1	18.0 kft	257	int at fl 180
113439		restart profile 1	18.0 kft	073	fl180 - 200/220
113605		Nev & JW calcs	19.5 kft	073	
113835		end profile 1 & start run 1.1	22.0 kft	070	fl 220
114139		end Run 1.1	22.0 kft	080	
114539	115340	Run 1.2	22.0 kft	255	fl220
115756	120335	Run 2.1	20.0 kft	088	towards Chilbolton
120609		video	16.5 kft	327	left recorder to RFC
120712	121639	Run 3.1	16.5 kft	259	fl 165
120908		nev JW cal	16.5 kft	257	
122125	122726	Run 4.1	13.0 kft	088	
123118	123257	Profile 2.1	15.0 - 17.0 kft	257	
123258	123525	Profile 2.2	17.0 - 15.0 kft	254	
123526	123641	Profile 2.3	15.0 - 15.4 kft	256	brief interruption
123720	123909	Profile 2.4	15.4 - 19.3 kft	254	should read 17.0kft
123909	124208	Profile 2.5	19.3 - 15.0 kft	257	should read 17.0kft
124520	124747	Profile 3.1	14.0 - 12.0 kft	082	
124747	125018	Profile 3.2	12.0 - 14.0 kft	073	
125018	125243	Profile 3.3	14.0 - 12.0 kft	074	
125150		nev zero			
125517		overhead Chilbolton	13.0 kft		eastbound
130000		overhead Chilbolton	13.0 kft		westbound
130000	130341	Profile 3.4	13.0 - 10.0 kft		
130341	131621	Run 5.1	10.0 kft	254	
131954	132955	Run 6.1	12.0 kft	079	
132147		nev zero	12.0 kft	072	
132640					DITM in error
133131					DITM heater on
133314					DITM heater off
133334	134238	Run 7.1	16.5 kft	256	
133628		video tapes changed	16.5 kft	256	
134652	135212	Run 8.1	18.0 kft	071	
134727		nev zero	18.0 kft	064	
135538	140448	Run 9.1	16.5 kft	251	
135734		nev & jw zeros	16.5 kft	257	
140831		nev zero	13.0 kft	091	
140845	141622	Run 10.1	13.0 - 11.7 kft	082	
141903	142448	Run 11.1	11.5 kft	259	
142807	143453	Run 12.1	13.0 kft	066	overhead Chilbolton at 143453 eastbound
144024			13.0 kft		overhead Chilbolton westbound
144431	145027	Run 13.1	9.5 kft	252	
145037	145250	Profile 4	9.5 - 7.5 kft	253	
145625	145908	Profile 5	7.6 - 5.0 kft	081	
145933		Run 14.1	5.0 kft	075	
150743			5.0 kft		overhead Chilbolton land Cranfield
154048					

B108 Track 05-JUL-05

PROJECT BRIEF: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies (KNB 04/07/05)

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems that lie within the temperature regime in which mixed-phase clouds are possible (typically 0 to -30C). In particular, we wish to examine the competing roles of

- primary ice nucleation
- secondary nucleation via the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of larger ice particles.
- other secondary ice nucleation mechanisms such as evaporative break-up
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamical environment within the cloud (and in particular the strength of embedded convective updraughts)

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the Camra radar facility at Chilbolton, Hants. The radar may identify features such as embedded convective cells or layers of supercooled liquid water that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft. Similarly, the aircraft can provide information on microphysical characteristics to aid interpretation of the radar data.

Weather conditions: A stratiform cloud band lying over or to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction, and hence to more easily penetrate identifiable cloud features on successive runs at the same altitude. Note that to avoid interference with Bournemouth airport, Chilbolton is NOT allowed to transmit in the sector 209 to 219 degrees true.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 (and SID-2). Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest.
- If functional, the Ice Nucleus counter (INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to a different set of conditions.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.

Sortie Brief: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 5th July 2005

Flight Number: B108

M.Sci: Jonathan A. Smith, Dave Kindred

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes and cloud dynamics in stratiform cloud systems in association with Chilbolton radar.

Sortie Location: Within a stratiform cloud system over/to the west of Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign “Radsearch”). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. In this case, the aircraft may fly a small butterfly pattern in which only one of the legs is parallel to the wind direction or radar azimuth. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles. On occasion, the aircraft flight legs may start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so will limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL50 to transit to operating area west of Chilbolton.
- b) T+20 When in a suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl (or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions) or to 1000 ft below the freezing level. Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL280 or to above cloud top (whichever is lower) (40 min)
- c) T+60 Establish start/end points of 40-60km of level flight legs along the azimuth which is being scanned by the radar. Fly these legs at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Duration of each leg ~ 5-10 minutes. Some legs may be extended into the overhead position of Chilbolton when requested from the ground.
- d) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern (see diagram)

- e) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- f) Repeat items c) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.

Chil bolton

Radio where we are
run ahead

Mission Scientist's Log

Jonathan Smith

Flight No **B.108**

Date **5th July '05**

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:29	4/0				3/8 Sc, hazy
"	climb	2800			base small cu, few hundred feet deep
					1/8 Cu below 3/8 Sc above, 1/8 St below
10:53	transit	5000	270		Sc layer base appears to be lower ahead, still above at moment
10:55	"	"	262		at top of Sc T = +4°C
10:57				52°N 14°W	met midscreen ↓
					20300 pm CPI small & large
11:01	"	"	181		much brighter now - no drops
R					streaming on midscreen now
					LWC on 8/W is 0.1 gm ⁻³
11:05	"	"	180	51.6°N 14°W	darker outside LWC approx. same
11:08					contact with Rad search
11:11					peak LWC of 0.8 gm ⁻³
	start P1		248		in cloud, quite bright LWC ~ 0.2 gm ⁻³
11:16	P1	6200	243		a cloud top Sc
	P1	6400			clearer again 7/8 Sc above
					clear to port on horizon
					wind 13 m/s 237 deg
11:20	P1	9800			back into cloud, base of upper layer
					LWC 0.2 gm ⁻³
11:22	P1	11000			SNOW on 2D & CPI
					clear blue sky to port.
11:23					ice crystals - needles on 2D

3/4

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....108.....

Date **5th** July.....

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:25					weather radar has main line stopping from Sierra River mouth / east my south Weymouth Pothol bill
11:25		14600			top of Sc level good meanwhile snow on 2D
		17000			pass higher + more (hazy layer) at the shore Cb ahead - much higher
	Chl → "	13000 / 20000			
					Kahira Helmbtz
					lower levels after that
	Chl " high	2/dR	→	5-6 km "	Plan ← 220 200 → ← 165 130 →
11:45					just miss the wings, on purpose Air Traffic are amused CCN falling sample
	can see 90 km	70 or 80 km			as length
11:49					pass through higher cloud nice tunnel ahead
	on pass				cloud was mixed phase ^{CPI} T-24 ^{2D} 25-50 μm
					CCN looks ok 2 samples Bgo
11:53	end R12				no cloud above 1/8 Cs at level 1/8 Cu 8/8 Sc below CCN 1/3 samples

AC

Mission Scientist's Log

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Date **5th July '05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1200	R2-1	FL 200	"in" 33		"connective structure 20km apart"
1201					2D sees some snow must be some small cloud
1202					"large snow" 2D, + approach small - "snow on camera"
	R3-1				"connective structure 20km away"
1209					into the cloud "seen on radar"
					small + small particles - 2D
					all liquid cloud
12:13					up draft is $\pm 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$
	and R3-1				in clear
12:21:18					into cloud - asked for zeron
					Nov. maybe been ok?
					just going in & out of tops on this run
					"saw both h →
					130-165 "
1220					into the line of cloud now
					170 → 150 saw both
1225					CPI sees rimed columns + 2D
1226		13000			mixed phase ^{or 2D} T - 7°
1231					2D saw some lumpy - - -
					2D seeing bits of - - -
12:32:20					out of tops
					"120-140 + overhead"
					out at 100 130

Traffic above

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.108**

 Date **5th July**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:39:33				509° 24M	Truffis again - now no Grant ahead of us, no higher cloud here 8/8 Ac ice crystal cloud in distance
					Out of cloud informately - "Fl100 on return"
12:51					Now zeroed, I enter cloud again.
12:52					2D sees small particles maybe drops CPI sees drops also T-4.5
12:53:14					CPI sees columns (+2D smell)
12:54:03		10 km	away at	FL130	T-6°C
12:55:14					overhead Chilbolton near tops of cloud eddies CPI plates drops spotted
					"slight differential z/dR" at this time
12:57:24					CPI grapsed, 2D yes + now snow some 3 mm across
12:59:25				T-6°C	2D spherical particles temperature can see second bed of rain beyond 80 km at 100 km
13:03:40					2D small stuff CPI - droplets
13:03:41	R5.1			start Fl100	'thin layer at 12000, clear 20 km wide, 70 km distance try and skim layer at 12000"
13:07:39					pass under the layer?
13:10					500µm & 200µm drops then large snow

Mission Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1311:18	5-1	10,000	255	509°N 2.1°W	T -1.7°C
1313					250µm droplets - clear images
1315:54					CI droplets up to 50µm medium AC with embedded Cu 3/8 below, no cloud above
1319:15		12000		T -5.6°C	droplets + a few columns
1322:10					rain
					"16500 ft for out"
1327:30		12000			in a thin cloud layer or haze "3.5km" 11000 ft?
					Cb to N
13:34	R21	FL 165	251		T -14.6
					'next run higher to skin top
					near tops of convection sq
					Devised temperature probe has broken
					180
				T _w -12°	large irregular ice 2mm(?)
					+ small droplets ~ 20µm
	R21				no cloud above, 3/8 AC
					"out of cloud 30km from Chilbotto"
13:45:00		FL180	186		~ haze layer or Ci at this level ahead
					very near top, nothing on
					redox at this altitude
					some turbulence (slight) apparently
					updraft was ~ ± 2 m s ⁻¹

"out of cloud turn"

"FL165 on out board"

Mission Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	"70	16km out		B FL	130 (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	crossed to	8km		to Chilleston	on turn
	9.1				approaching system again no Ci above
					nothing on weather radar (inflight)
					bumpy
14:00:20	start				"all ice" on pass thro' system
	10.1	130			miss the system this time
					skim tops of system to starboard
					just under top of system to port
				"next out at FL 115	out board)
14:7					T411 angular, v. large 6000µm drops
14:20:3	11.1	115			Start R 11.1
					only droplets, + patches of
14:19:50					mixed phase
14:20					only droplets,
					to "back at FL 130" + overhead
					"not much beyond 50km"
14: 14:30		FL 130	74		just over top of system
					T -4.5°C
					layer of As to starboard
14:					16 km
out					droplets + bit of ice
14: 14:40		overhead		Chilleston	
14:30		10km E of		↑	

King

Transit FLoSo

~18000 Mast Tops (6cm) 20-22kft

135-
2000

Cloud 6900
5000

R1.1 → 22.0kft

1.2 ← 22.0kft

2.1 → 20.0kft

3.1 ← 16.5kft

4.1 → 13.0kft

De-iced Temp?

T/o 1048

Land 1541.

5.1 ← 10.0kft.

6.1 → 12kft

4:53

7.1 ← 16.5kft

8.1 → 18.0kft

9.1 ← 16.5kft

10.1 → 13.0kft

11.1 ← 11.5kft

12.1 → 13.0kft 0/H ②

13.1 ← 9.5kft

De-Brief 17.15

Return Transit 050.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B108

Date: 05/07/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:15:07	337	0.7	484	3000	262	375	1	841	200	1	P1 Ascent from FL50
11:16:10	12	0.8	521	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL60
11:17:16	16	0.1	525	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	70
11:18:24	17	0.09	525	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80
11:19:33	21	0.09	527	3000	107	75	?	0	0	0	90 (FFSSP dau slow by 1.5s)
11:20:40	10	0.5	573	3000	18	800	3	50	3000	3	100
11:21:50	14	0.1	587	10	14	325	6	1483	1000	6	110
11:22:50	70	0.24	588	100	52	600	6	2100	1000	6	120
11:23:50	3	0	592	1000	174	750	3	7800	3000	3	130
11:24:50	97	0.57	605	700	195	800	3	6633	3000	3	140
11:26:04	19	0.1	616	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	150
11:27:07	46	0.12	624	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	160
11:28:10	132	0.13	624	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	170
11:29:08	92	0.11	624	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL180 P1 interrupted
11:34:38	206	0.1	624	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	P1 restarted FL180
11:35:36	8	0.09	624	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL190
11:35:33	4	0.07	624	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	200
11:36:31	10	0.09	624	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	210
11:38:36	40	0.35	628	1000	500	800	3	Missed data	1000	3	220 end of P1 and start of run 1.1
11:41:35	16	0.9	628	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	end Run 1.1 FL220
11:45:18	14	0.09	628	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 1.2 @ FL220
11:47:00	12	0.11	628	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:49:00	7	0.11	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Passed through turret, mixed phase
11:51:00	5	0.14	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:53:00	11	0.1	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:53:40	19	0.1	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 1.2
11:57:55	39	0.09	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 2.1 @ FL200
11:59:00	39	0.09	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:01:00	39	0.09	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Passed through turret
12:03:33	29	0.1	633	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 2.1
12:07:11	63	0.14	659	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 3.1 @ FL165
12:09:00	218	0.65	661	3000	127	800	8	4741	4000	8	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:11:00	183	0.12	678	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:13:00	155	0.12	681	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Missed turret again snow
12:15:00	140	0.11	681	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Changing record method to
12:16:37	33	0.09	681	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Take in turrets End of run 3.1
12:21:25	106	0.11	683	3000	161	250	1	5625	250	1	Start Run 4.1 @ FL130
12:23:00	101	0.1	690	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:24:14					1615	200	1	2985	300	1	
12:25:00	16	0.1	692	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:25:42					455	800	5	39566	1000	5	
12:27:26	15	0.69	712	3000	500	425	8	2075	800	8	End of run 4.1
12:31:18					33	775	3	983	3000	3	Start saw tooth @ FL 150
12:32:					small	Small	1				FL 160
12:33:59	256	0.13	769	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 170
12:34:10	254	0.11	769	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 160
12:35:16	221	0.11	769	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL150
12:36:20	Nothing	Of	Interest								153 interup
12:37:05	Nothing	Of	Interest								FL 153 restart
12:38:00	107	0.12	769	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 160
12:39:02	18	0.09	769	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL170
12:40:45	15	0.09	769	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL160
12:41:52	51	0.1	769	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 150 end of saw tooth
12:45:18	50	0.11	770	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start saw tooth @ FL 140
12:46:28	316	0.12	770	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 130
12:47:37	388	0.12	770	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 120
12:49:07	229	0.11	770	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 130
12:50:15	243	0.12	770	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 140
12:51:31	122	0.1	770	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 130
12:52:40	13	0.08	774	100	277	800	5	15500	1000	5	FL 120
12:54:03	14	0.2	786	3000	23	600	5	75	1000	5	FL 130 end of saw tooth
13:00:20	19	0.65	814	300	23	300	6	2500	250	6	Start p descent @ FL130
13:01:27	25	0.81	823	10	2	400	5	8	400	5	FL 120

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:02:30	29	0.1	823	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL 110
13:03:30	18	0.65	835	3000	967	150	1	108	200	1	FL 100 end of P start or run 5.1
13:05:00	5	0.83	859	3000	122	150	1	0	0	0	N.B. 1 – droplets not large drops
13:07:00	47	0.09	863	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:09:00	65	0.1	863	3000	21	75	1	0	0	0	
13:11:00	57	0.8	913	3000	88	550	8	3466	3000	8	
13:12:10	30	1.06	956	1000	136	800	3	14234	6400	3	Mixed, 3 masking 1
13:13:00	120	0.2			108	325	1	1116	400	1	
13:15:00	107	0.38	1037	100	91	650	3	6354	3000	3	Very small droplets also
13:16:21	134	0.11	1062	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 5.1
13:19:53	13	0.17	1090	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 6.1 @ FL 120
13:21:00	30	0.09	1091	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:23:0	21	0.3	1144	3000	low	100	1	0	0	0	
13:25:00	575	0.9	1189	3000	383	775	8	26300	2000	8	
13:27:00	54	0.11	1231	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:29:00	241	0.12	1231	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:29:52	105	0.1	1231	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 6.1
13:33:30	12	0.08	1231	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 7.1 @ FL 170
13:35:00	13	0.09	1231	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:37:00	17	0.08	1231	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:39:00	31	0.4	1233	100	89	800	8	5000	2000	8	LARGE ICE PARTICLES
13:41:00	15	0.08	1236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:42:37	15	0.08	1236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 7.1
13:46:47	16	0.11	1236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 8.1 @ FL 180
13:48:00	9	0.08	1236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:50:00	11	0.08	1236	1000	50	575	8	1000	2000	8	Large Ice Particles
13:52:10	17	0.09	1236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 8.1
13:55:37	24	0.08	1236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 9.1 @ FL 165
13:57:00	24	0.09	1236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
13:59:00	3	0.07	1238	100	100	800	8	800	2000	8	Large ice particles
14:01:00	30	0.08	1238	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:03:00	15	0.08	1238	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B108

Date: 05/07/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:04:43	12	0.07	1238	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 9.1
14:08:36	22	0.08	1238	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 10.1 @FL 130
14:10:00	19	0.09	1238	100	100	150	8	0	0	0	
14:12:00	27	0.08	1238	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:14:00	21	0.45	1239	100	120	100	5	0	0	0	
14:14:52	51	1.06	1246	3000	33	800	6	3888	2000	8	End of run 10.1
14:18:59	105	0.5	1297	300	130	700	8	6000	800	8	Start of run 11.1 @ FL115
14:20:00	139	0.5	1331	3000	18	100	1	3400	800	8	
14:22:00	26	0.1	1366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:24:00	9	0.08	1366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:24:39	33	0.08	1366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 11.1
14:28:04	25	0.09	1366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 12.1 @ FL130
14:30:00	7	0.08	1366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:32:00	12	0.08	1366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:34:53	12	0.32	1384	3000	13	475	1/5	375	1000	8	End Run 12.1 Coincident over CB
14:36:00	473	0.62	1427	3000	792	800	8	40000	4000	8	
14:38:00	50	1.2	1464	3000	22	300	1	1450	400	1	
14:40:40	5	0.07	1489	100	50	625	5	2000	800	5	End of run 12.1
14:44:30	51	0.29	1627	3000	25	75	1	0	0	0	Start run 13.1
14:45:30					1200	400	1	12000	1000	1	
14:46:00	47	0.09	1650	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:48:00	124	0.18	1655	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:50:00	47	0.09	1692	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:50:23	47										End of Run 13.1
14:50:30	34	0.15	1694	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Profile 4 descent @ FL95
14:51:10	35	0.09	1694	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	90
14:52:07	52	0.09	1695	3000	0	0	0	0	0	0	80
14:52:50	32	0.09	1696	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	75 interupt
14:56:25	112	0.09	1696	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	75 restart called P5
14:57:05	130	0.09	1696	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	70
14:58:02	66	0.09	1696	3000	12	175	1	0	0	0	60
14:59:11	22	0.7	1708	3000	679	250	1	16.67	250	1	50 end P4 and start run 14.1

Flight Bφφ8
CWVC

5/7/05
Tuesday

Tried aligning ADA, ^{from scratch} seemed to be going OK but couldn't get couples aligned at all.

Is the ~~too~~ laser aligned with bench?

CPI cleaned windows, PDS levels are now low & usage near optimal.

other notes :-

Synchronised CPI time with HORACE.

1102:

CPI going crazy - ~~and~~ we are
in thick cloud.

1105 :-

CPI ok now - do not trust
data ~~from~~ in the above time interval
(1102 - 1105)

↓

When in thick water cloud, cpi
seems to drop with water and
go mad ~~with water~~

↓

When this happens 90 DC levels
go high

0.4×10^{-3}

all $0^{\circ} 0^{\circ}$

Profile 1.0 start

@ 111507

- we see droplets still in this profile
- then come out of cloud.

we see columns now

↓

we are going into both
mixed phase & liquid clouds.

ZDC reports snow but CPI doesn't

- CPI is seeing droplets also.
- Perhaps ZDC is more sensitive to
snow?

Profile stop

112931

Profile 1.0 restarted

113438

columns, droplets, plates - polymers

End profile 1

113835

Start Run ~~profile~~ 1 113835

End NA Truch Run 1 114132
can't follow flight sensor

Start Run 1-2 114532 FL 220

ice short columns - droplets now

clear of cloud

~~Start~~ End Run 1-2 115340

Start 2-1 115756 FL 200
(towards Dulles)

- mixed particles -
plates & droplets

out of cloud

End of run 2-1 120335

NOW
Turn away from Dulles & fly run
165°?

Start run 3-1 120712 FL 165

Snow! droplets
- plates & stellars

clear

- droplets
clear

- ice

End run 3-1 121639 FL 165

Start run 4-1 122125

drop, ice

drops - 2X sees drops also.

mixed phase, columns etc

End an 4.1 (22726)

Now saw-tooth plan ...

Start profile sawtooth 2.1 123118

droplets

End profile 2.1

→ Start profile 2.2 123258

no cloud?

End profile 2.2 123525

→ Start profile 2.3 123526
interrupted (traffic above).
123647

→ restarted^{as} (2.4) 123720

nothing 123909

→ Start 25 123009

nothing
End 124208

turn back ... (a lot of air traffic)
here ...

Saw both again

Start profile 3.1 124520

nothing
End 124747

→ Start profile 3.2 124747

nothing
End 125018

→ Start profile 3.3 125018
cloud
droplets

End 125243

columns, med
droplets @ top of saw tooth

End
→

Start

columns, plate

droplets
group

* 2DC - 3000 μ m particles
columns & small ice (11-14 μ m)
-6 €

End

→ Start no call

- ice
- droplets

1207111

Start Run 5-1 130361

droplets
2DC say 300 μ m droplet?

(the 2DC does oversize)
droplets however

as does the CPI...

droplets
↓

larger droplets

↓
same ice

↓
droplets

End Run 5-1 131621

Start Run 6.1 131954

droplets, columns same mixed,

mixed plane

mostly ice

End Run 6.1 132955

Start Run 7.1 133334

1338 cloud - small
large ice, columns, p

nothing
End run 7.1 134248 FC 165

Start Run 8.1 134652
large ice & small ice
ZDC saw 3000 μ m ice!

End 135212

Start Run 9.1 135538

ice, all ice

End run 9.1 140448

Start Run 10.1 140845

ice 1409

some columns

End run 10.1 141622

Start Run 11.1 141903

just droplets now
mixed plane 2420
drops

End Run 11.1 142448

Start Run 12.1 142807

droplets
down

droplets/columns

End Run 12.1 143453
(over the bottom)

droplets
mixed
droplets
etc

not in a run

Start Run 13.1 144431

droplets; so does 2DE

24.50
drop

End Run 13.1 145027

Start profile (descent) 4 145037

Droplets

End - 145120

Start profile 5 145625

Big droplets
End 145908

Start Run 14.1 145933

Droplets - no ice
& drops

End Run 14.1

Stopped searching @ 18:20
→ Heavy rain.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B108**

Date: 05/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B108

Date: 05/07/05

Instruments

1. Video – inboard recorder screen in standby
2. FFC obscured by snow , RFC used as alternative
Tail anti-ice didn't seem as effective at clearing camera as for B107
3. FM's PC froze once towards end of science, rebooted ok
4. RFC picture on FM's display very dark; video display and recording ok
5. DFC poor focus
6. Deiced Rosemount diverged from Non deiced and then straight lined indicating 90C
Problem noticed about 13:20
7. no dial tone on SATCOM H phone

Rack instrument status

ADA - not working

CPI, Cloud Physics & AMS – all fine

CVI ok

CCN – good operation

Aircraft

FFC not working before flight, sorted by DFL.

Probable loose connection at camera location.

